

Quantum Bound State: Single Particle or Density?

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A quantum single particle bound state involves a single particle, like a classical bound state, but it also involves spatial densities like a Maxwell-Boltzmann gas. For instance, a single particle has potential energy $V(x)$ at x , while a density $\rho(x)$ has potential energy $V(x) \rho(x)$. As a result, there seems to be a dichotomy. How does one solve the problem of single particle bound state? Does one use the concept of a single particle or of a density $\rho(x)$? We argue that one focuses on a single particle, but with an added piece of physics. In classical physics, a particle with constant momentum (speed) moves in a deterministic way described by $x=vt$. On average, a quantum single particle creates its own ruler gradation and a sense of a direction in space through $\exp(ipx)$ which maps to 1 via $\exp(-ipx) \exp(ipx)$. A single quantum bound particle which gives the semblance of an entity moving in a straight line back and forth (in a distance of the same order of \hbar/p) needs to create a semblance of acceleration as an average single particle. As a result, one may think of an ensemble i.e. $W(x)=\sum_p a(p)\exp(ipx)$. The difference with a free particle is that one has interference (+p's and -p's) which readily display a spatial $W(x)$ which may ultimately be linked to a spatial density through $W^*(x)W(x)$. Thus, one now has the idea of spatial density which exists in a Maxwell-Boltzmann gas, This, however, is a consequence of the single particle approach.

We argue that the single particle viewpoint leads to the spatial density one and not vice versa because of the way $KE(x)+V(x) = E$ is treated. If one writes $V(x)=\sum_k V_k \exp(ikx)$, one does not write: $KE(x) = \sum_k b_k \exp(ikx)$. We argue the reason is that such a $KE(x)$ is not normalized so as to create the sense of a single particle. We argue that such a normalization leads to: $KE(x) = \{\sum_p a(p) p^2/2m \exp(ipx)\} / W(x)$ meaning that on average one has a moving entity. $V(x)$, on the other hand, is not a moving entity.

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In classical mechanics, one thinks of a single particle acted on by a force $F(x)$. It accelerates, having a different $v(x)$ at each x . In terms of energy, the particle has a potential energy of $V(x)$ at x as well as a kinetic adding to E . A bound particle moves back and forth in time between endpoints. (Here we consider a conservative force.)

In classical statistical mechanics with a potential $V(x)$ present, one thinks in terms of spatial densities as one has many particles. In such a case, classical mechanics pertains to each particle when they are not colliding, but the collisions create a kinetic energy distribution at each x point which has the same probability $P(KE \text{ single particle})= C \exp(- KE/T)$. This leads to the concept of an average pressure per particle which is a function of T , but not x . If there are more particles in one $x \pm dx/2$ than another, a spatial density arises. In such a case, Force $= -dV/dx$ acts on a density, not a single particle at x and a balance equation is established at the density and not the single particle level. In particular:

$$\text{Pressure}(x+dx) - \text{Pressure}(x) = -dV/dx \text{ density}(x) \quad ((1))$$

If pressure = density(x) RT (ideal gas law), one obtains an differential equation in density(x) which may be solved to yield: density(x) = exp(-V(x)/T). Thus one may combine the two density pieces to obtain:

$$\text{Density(single particle)} = C \exp(- (KE+V(x))/T) \quad ((2))$$

Thus, applying force to a single particle in a classical gas only yields an equation for its motion when collisions do not occur. This is not the full picture. It is a force analysis at the density(x) level (using PV=nRT i.e. a thermodynamic type force called pressure) which solves the full problem. One may think of exp(-V/T) being associated with a single particle as well as the average of exp(-KE/T) in a kind of quantum mechanical way. This then means that a single particle spends less time in some regions than others i.e. has a spatial density, but this result does not follow from inherent single particle properties, but from overall statistical mechanical properties, in particular exp(-KE/T) which requires many particles colliding to create this situation.

The question arises: What does one do for a single particle quantum system? There is one particle, suggesting a classical mechanical approach acting on a single particle, yet there is a quantum spatial density $W^*(x)W(x)$, suggesting a classical statistical mechanical gas approach. Which approach solves the problem? We argue that it is the single particle approach which solves the problem, but it then leads to the spatial density picture.

Time-Independent Schrodinger Equation

The time independent Schrodinger equation is:

$$-\frac{1}{2m} \frac{d^2W}{dx^2} + V(x) W(x) = E_n W(x) \quad ((3))$$

$W(x)$ is called the wavefunction and has boundary conditions imposed at +/- infinite usually i.e. it tends to 0 at these points. For an infinite well potential it tends to 0 at the walls. ((3)) may be written as:

$$\left\{ \sum_p a(p) \frac{p^2}{2m} \exp(ipx) \right\} / W(x) + V(x) = E_n \quad ((4))$$

where $W(x) = \sum_p a(p) \exp(ipx)$.

((4)) is of the form of a classical single particle conservation of energy equation with the first term on the LHS being $KE_{\text{classical}}(x)$. One may note that this term appears to be a normalized average, but an unusual one:

$$KE_{\text{classical}}(x) = \left\{ \sum_p a(p) \frac{p^2}{2m} \exp(ipx) \right\} / W(x) \quad ((5))$$

As a first step, one may write $V(x)$ in ((3)) as $\sum_k V_k \exp(ikx)$, but $KE_{\text{classical}}(x)$ is not treated in the same way. A Fourier series is not taken directly of $KE_{\text{classical}}(x)$. Why are the two treated differently? $V(x)$ represents the cause of force and does not move (as an approximation). On the other hand, the classical particle moves from x to x changing speed.

Thus even though $KE(x)$ and $V(x)$ are both energies dependent on x , one contains dynamics (in x) while the other does not. In a classical picture, a particle has a different $v(x)$ (speed) at each x .

In a quantum picture, as seen in ((4)), the particle has the usual classical kinetic energy $pp/2m$, but an unusual unnormalized probability $\exp(ipx)$. The probability is normalized because one needs a probability adding to 1 as momentum and kinetic energies are properties of a single particle. By writing a normalized probability (even one involving interference we argue), one explicitly states the existence of an entity with the particular property (e.g. p , $pp/2m$ etc). $V(x)$, on the other hand, delivers force or impulse hits, "k" from $\exp(ikx)$ does not define it as an entity with this particular property as part of an average. Thus the normalization $W(x)$ indicates a single particle view.

Why should a single particle with constant momentum be described by $\exp(ipx)$? We have argued in previous notes that a single particle with constant p , representing impulse force, defines a straight line in space together with its ruler graduations. In other words, it is an eigenfunction of the translation operator multiplied by $-i$ i.e. $-id/dx \exp(ipx) = p \exp(ipx)$. $\exp(ipx)$ maps into a uniform probability through $\exp(-ipx)\exp(ipx) = 1$. Thus constant impulse hits are linked with two x -probability distributions $\cos(px)$ and $\sin(px)$. If no interference occurs, i.e. no impulse hits, one may not notice these. In a bound state, however, $V(x)$ renders impulse hits and $-p$ and p ensure that $\exp(-ipx) + \exp(+ipx)$ terms (even parity) yield $\cos(px)$ type terms. These affect the probability of impulse hits at different x points. The hit is still p , but $\cos(px)$ yields different probabilities. In fact, a resonance is created through hits with $V(x)$ to yield a $W(x) = \text{Sum over } a(p)\exp(ipx)$. Thus $\exp(ipx)$ describes a free particle with constant p and how it moves in space, while $W(x)$ describes a bound particle and how it moves in space. The latter, however, includes both forward and backwards motion.

Single Particle Bound Motion Creates the Idea of Density

According to the arguments above, single particle superposition, assuming $\exp(ipx)$ describes a constant momentum particle. A superposition of these may be created through the interaction with a $V(x)$ to create an average $KE(x)$ which is classical. The consequence, however, is that a real $W(x)$ (normalization constant) is created. If $\exp(ipx)\exp(-ipx) = 1$ represents spatial probability, then $W(x)W(x)$ represents spatial probability for a single quantum bound particle. This, however, implies a spatial density which reminds one of classical statistical mechanics. In classical statistical mechanics, however, the statistical feature is in the collisions which lead to $\exp(-KE/T)$. The spatial density is created by shifting particles so that the entropic force $PV = \text{density}(x) RT$ balances the mechanical one $-dV/dx \text{ density}(x)$. Thus one solves the problem by considering densities not a single particle.

We argue that a quantum single particle bound state is the opposite. It is the single particle solution which creates the superposition based density. This leads to two ways of viewing the quantum bound state. (Alternatively, one may consider a single particle, but it is acted on by entropic forces which are really the result of many particles colliding and establishing an equilibrium.)

One may first consider only the single particle picture using ((4)). This yields $W(x)$ which then yields $\text{density}(x)=W(x)W(x)$. $\text{density}(x)$ may then be used to create physical energy terms such as:

$$\text{Potential energy}(x) = \text{density}(x) V(x) \quad \text{and overall kinetic energy}(x) = W(x) (-1/2m d/dx dW/dx) \quad ((6))$$

One may notice the pattern of: $W(x)$ (operator) $W(x)$ with operator =1 for density.

Is there a contradiction to using $V(x)$ as the potential energy of a single particle and $V(x)$ $\text{density}(x)$ as the physical potential energy for a $\text{density}(x)$ representing the same single particle? $V(x)$ as applied to a single particle is directly linked with force through $-dV/dx$ while $W(x) = \text{Sum over } a(p)\exp(ipx)$ may also be considered as delivering impulse hits. Thus, unlike classical statistical mechanics, a balance does not occur at the density level, but at the single particle level with various constant p interfering $\exp(ipx)$'s ultimately creating the balance. The key idea, we argue, is that one uses $W(x)$ as a normalization for the single particle to show that it is an entity. This allows one to form a single particle average ((5)). Given an equation for a single particle: $KE_{\text{classical}}(\text{single particle})(x) + V(x) = E$, one may always multiply both sides by $\text{density}(x)$ to obtain a physical equation reflecting physical densities present. Thus the two approaches are consistent.

The difference with classical statistical mechanics is that one creates a statistical energy conservation balance using a single particle ensemble based on $\exp(ipx)$ single particle constant momentum states that are normalized. It is this normalization which later becomes spatial density $W(x)W(x)$ in the single particle bound system.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we argue that a quantum mechanical single particle bound system is really a single particle statistical energy balance system. The single particle nature is seen from the form $KE_{\text{classical}}(x)+V(x) = E_n$ which holds for every energy level. A classical mechanical scenario considers a single particle which accelerates i.e. changes $v(x)$ at each x . We argue that a quantum free particle defines a line in space with ruler gradations i.e. $\exp(ipx)$. These are linked to the impulse hit delivered by p . Thus in a potential $V(x)$ which may deliver impulse hits through $V(x)=\text{Sum over } k V_k \exp(ikx)$, an ensemble of $\exp(ipx)$'s arises. One does not simply take the Fourier series of $KE(x)$ classical because the single particle is an entity with single particle values (e.g. $pp/2m$) which may be averaged. This notion of average requires a normalization to 1 even though unusual interfering unnormalized probabilities $\exp(ipx)$ are used.

Thus the Schrodinger equation has the appearance of a single particle equation, although it uses probabilities associated with the single particle states $\exp(ipx)$. A kind of resonance is created which in turn leads to a density $W(x)W(x)$. As a result, there are physical quantities like potential energy at x i.e. $V(x)$ $\text{density}(x) \{ W(x) \text{ operator } W(x) \}$, but these arise after one uses the single particle concept to find $W(x)$. Thus quantum mechanical bound states do not seem to be based on classical $\text{density}(x)$, but rather on a statistical approach associated with interfering single particle $\exp(ipx)$ "probabilities".